

Deliverable 3.1.2.1

DESIGN THINKING WORKSHOP FOR INDUSTRY PARTNERS

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D3.1.2.1 Design Thinking Workshop for Industry Partners

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General Information

Summary

The primary objective of this deliverable is to engage industry stakeholders early in the platform's development to ensure it aligns with industry needs, fosters adoption, and facilitates data sharing. By incorporating their feedback, the project team aims to identify critical requirements and enablers that will enhance the platform's usability and incentivize data contributions from partners. The scope and roles of these stakeholders are further discussed in [1].

Using the industry network established in D3.1.1.1, this deliverable documents a first workshop designed to gauge industry interests and priorities for the envisioned NFDI4Energy platform. Embedded within a design science research framework as described in [2], this workshop, held in November 2023 in Karlsruhe, brought together seven partners from the network. The insights gained form an initial set of requirements, which will be refined and detailed further in D3.1.2.2.

Related Deliverables: D3.1.2.1; D3.1.2.2

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Figure 1 - Task Area 3 connections to other Task Areas within the NFDI4Energy consortium.

This deliverable covers the following tasks, as part of M3.1, illustrated in Fig.1:

- Describe the workshop design,
- Describe the results of this workshop in the form of initial requirements for platform adoption and data sharing.

Deliverable

1. Workshop Design

The Design Thinking workshop was structured to achieve three primary objectives:

- Identify key drivers and challenges of open data for the energy sector.
- Generate concrete requirements for an open data platform.
- Prioritize these requirements based on industry relevance.

First Part:

To gather insights on drivers and challenges, we employed a fishbowl discussion method, facilitating an open and dynamic exchange (following the approach in [3]). This approach involved placing industry partners in an inner circle as the main discussants, while energy researchers formed an outer circle, observing and posing questions into the inner circle for approximately one hour. The process was as follows:

- Industry participants discussed open data drivers and challenges from the energy sector's perspective within **the inner circle**.
- **The outer circle** listened closely, noting open questions and key insights on Post-it notes, which were then asked to the inner circle, as soon as the discussion toned down.

Second Part:

For the ideation phase, we applied the Conversation Café methodology, as outlined in [4], which ran for approximately 45 minutes. Participants were divided into two groups: one focused on generating features that align with the identified open data drivers, while the other worked on solutions for the identified challenges. The process followed these steps:

1. Individual Ideation:

Each participant spent 10 minutes individually brainstorming and noting ideas—either features or solutions, depending on their group assignment—on Post-it notes.

2. Group Discussion:

Participants then gathered in their groups to discuss, cluster, and consolidate ideas, capturing these shared results on posters. Each group briefly presented their outcomes at the end.

Third Part:

In the workshop's final phase, all participants were invited to prioritize the most important features and solutions proposed in the conversation café. Participants moved to the posters and marked the features or solutions they considered most critical. Each individual provided a brief justification for their choices, fostering a shared understanding of priorities across the group.

This structured, interactive approach provided a comprehensive view of the industry's needs and challenges, as well as collaborative solutions, establishing a prioritized framework for developing an effective open data platform for the energy sector.

2. Workshop Results

Seven industry partners from our network participated in this workshop. The findings highlight key opportunities in open data, including enhanced collaboration, improved accessibility, and support for innovation, indicating a clear demand for open data within the industry. However, significant hurdles related to data sharing—specifically in data provision and data requests—were also identified and are

summarized in Tables 1 and 2. Proposed solutions to these challenges will inform the development of concrete platform requirements moving forward.

Table 1 - Challenges in data provision and proposed solutions.

Category	Challenge	Description	Solution
Ease of Provision	Data privacy and Ownership	Privacy concerns and data ownership constraints create barriers to open data sharing, especially when data includes sensitive customer or operational information.	Provide tools for data anonymization and allow selective sharing options to control access, such as bilateral data exchange where companies can selectively choose partners for data sharing.
	Legal uncertainty	Organizations face uncertainty around legal implications and compliance when sharing open data, which can discourage participation.	Present examples of other companies sharing data successfully and legally to reduce perceived risks. Include legal guidelines and case studies to help users navigate these challenges.
	Data manipulation	There is a risk of data being manipulated to gain market advantage, leading to distrust.	Implement mechanisms to cross-reference data with existing research to verify accuracy. Peer-review processes can further validate data quality and reliability.
	Data format	The lack of standardized data formats makes data sharing and integration cumbersome and time-consuming.	Establish and promote standardized data formats, along with clear guidelines on formatting and sharing data, making it easier for users to interpret and integrate data.
Motivation	Incentives	Without clear benefits, organizations may be reluctant to share data.	Develop incentives such as certification standards that recognize quality and privacy compliance, a “give-to-get” model where data contributors receive access to other data in return, and brand visibility opportunities, such as displaying company logos on the platform to enhance reputation.
	Collaborative Research	Lack of targeted collaboration can reduce the value of open data for some stakeholders.	Encourage collaborative research by helping users find suitable research partners and create shared research questions, driving mutual benefits and stronger engagement.

Table 2 - Challenges in data request and proposed solutions.

Category	Challenge	Description	Solution
Usage	Structuring efforts	Preparing and structuring data for open sharing requires significant effort, which can deter organizations.	Offer web services and standardized APIs to streamline the data structuring and sharing process, reducing the technical burden on organizations.

	Bureaucratic and procedural hurdles	Internal bureaucratic processes can slow down or block data sharing efforts.	The platform could provide ready-to-use data templates and best practices to simplify data preparation and submission, facilitating smoother internal approvals.
	Data silos	Many organizations work in isolated data silos, limiting cross-industry insights.	Establish a central repository with standardized and accessible data formats to encourage data sharing across sectors.
	Inconsistent data quality and format	Data from different sources often vary in quality and format, complicating usage and integration.	Implement automated peer review and consistency checks, supported by standardized APIs and web services for seamless data integration and interoperability.
Seeking Data	Limited direct access	Users face limited direct access to certain datasets, especially sensitive or high-value data.	Provide synthetic data tools as a way to simulate real-world data, making accessible versions of proprietary data while protecting sensitive information.
	Data discovery	Discovering relevant datasets is often a time-consuming process due to lack of centralized resources.	Utilize APIs and web services to streamline data discovery and facilitate direct access to a diverse range of datasets.

To address general needs, the platform should incorporate clear best practices and guidelines on data formatting, documentation, and sharing processes to streamline user contributions and ensure consistency. Additionally, decision-making tools such as Jupyter notebooks, scripts, and interoperability matrices would enhance data analysis capabilities, making the platform more valuable for diverse stakeholders. A feature highlighting trending research questions and popular data topics would further guide users toward high-impact projects and foster collaborative opportunities within the community.

Platform Requirements

Based on the challenges and solutions identified, here are the key requirements for an effective open data platform:

1. **Data Privacy and Anonymization Tools:**
Integrate automated anonymization services and selective sharing options to support data privacy and offer control over access, enabling users to share data without risking sensitive information.
2. **Standardized Data Formats and Documentation Guidelines:**
Establish standardized formats and comprehensive documentation guidelines to ensure consistency and ease of use, reducing the burden on data providers and improving data integration for users.
3. **Legal Guidance and Assurance Mechanisms:**
Provide legal guidelines, examples, and a checklist to help users navigate compliance issues.

A certification system for privacy and quality compliance would also increase user confidence.

4. **Quality Assurance through Peer Review:**

Implement an automated peer-review process to validate data quality and consistency, with options for manual review as necessary. This helps ensure reliability and builds trust in the data.

5. **Incentive Mechanisms:**

Introduce a range of incentives, including a “give-to-get” model, brand visibility, and certification for data quality. Highlight collaborative research opportunities to drive engagement and add value for contributors.

6. **Centralized Data Repository with API Access:**

Develop a centralized, easily navigable repository supported by standardized APIs for efficient data discovery and seamless access. This would address challenges related to data silos and ease of access.

7. **Data Discovery and Decision-Support Tools:**

Include tools like Jupyter notebooks, scripts, and interoperability matrices to support data analysis and practical decision-making, making the platform more attractive for industry users.

8. **Showcase of Trending Topics and Research:**

Feature a section highlighting trending research questions and topics to guide users towards high-impact areas and encourage collaboration on relevant issues.

9. **Synthetic Data for Sensitive Datasets:**

Provide synthetic data options where real-world data access is restricted, allowing users to experiment with realistic datasets while maintaining confidentiality.

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